

FAIRYTALES IN TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN A PRIMARY EDUCATION

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***Abstract.** This article examines the using of fairy tales in Primary Education English classes. There are some suggestions for teachers why stories are necessary for young learners and about using fairy tales in English primary classes.*

***Key words.** Fairytales, teacher, children, pupils, illustrations, English, stories, language, listening, education, reading, characters, interesting.*

Introduction. Story telling is always known as an essential communication role in early human lives. It is the most important way of organizing first experience. They are not only the atmosphere of mystery and wonder as everyone thinks fairy tales are unique but also they cause the magic world to be comprehended by young learners. Children usually grown up by listening tales in their mother tongue. Because of this, even young children know what is going to happen and how to respond in these situations. Fairy tales have been used for a long time as a valuable resource in teaching language. They can be supposed as one of the great models for teaching since they have a clearly-set frame, a pre-defined terminology, short structure, a good atmosphere and plot. And they also encourage pupils to learn English. This research paper gives causes for using fairytales in English classes, what stories are perfect in primary education and what kind of activities can be beneficial in teaching foreign language.

Main part

Nowadays, due to the height of the need for foreign languages, a lot of research is being conducted on the methods of teaching languages to children. Children usually grow up by listening fairytales in their mother tongue. Storytelling can be a

perfect Introduction in teaching languages as stories are very suitable for children character. Fairy tales play an important role in children's lives. The main task of fairy tales is to tell children about the world in an understandable language. Ethics and aesthetics play an important role in fairy tales. They are divided into several types and they are for girls and boys. Fairy tales for girls mainly about housework, cleanliness, neatness, elegance and so on. The topics such as "Zumrad and Price" can be obtained. If we relate them to boys, then mainly external world, strength, courage, bravery and skills, professions are talked. In addition, children improve their behavior and respect surroundings.

Research by psychologists shows that the life of a child is programmed in their loved fairy tales. "Tell me what your favorite fairy tale is, I will tell you who you are" – this is famous saying of psychologists. Parents can learn fairy tale therapy on their own, but psychological counseling is better. Psychologists choose special fairy tales to influence gentle on the child's behavior. [Ermolina M.V. 2012] Moreover, it's the best way to attract pupils' attention by using interesting teaching methods like story telling.

In work of Asuncion Barreras Gomes "How to use tales for the teaching of vocabulary and grammar in a primary education English class" [2010: 32] there are a number of reasons why teachers use children's stories:

- The fairy tale is perfect option for children to instill the love to education, as it causes the positive attitude and help children to keep studying.
- Stories improve the imagination. the processes of reading and listening of the stories make children to visualize the pictures from the text in their mind. Also stories give the general information about the world, cultures, human society and moreover, the stories give the understanding of what is evil and what is good, because the stories give the description of different character, their behavior and attitudes of another characters to the villains, thus, it teaches how children should behave for being accepted by others in the society.

• In nine to twelve years children learn to appreciate the other's point of view and at this period the stories about friendship, family relation should be included in educational program. These types of stories will provide children with the relation problems and how to cope with them. According to the Brumfit, Moon and Tongue 1991: 185, for simplifying the process of learning language, it will be more beneficial if the stories will be related with the children's daily life experiences.

• Stories are a useful tool in linking fantasy and imagination with the child's real world. So children can make sense of their everyday life.

• any kind of literature, including the fairy tales have emotional and social values. The process of the storytelling may cause a response of laughter, sadness, excitement and anticipations that improve the social and emotional developing. Because the process of storytelling is the process of sharing the social experience.

• Pupils love listening to fairy tales over and over again. This allows children learn the new words faster and easier.

• Pupils develop their general knowledge and listening and concentration by listening to fairy tales. In addition, the using fairy tales, which usually contain a lot of direct speech, helps children advance intonation is used to express attitudes and feelings.

• Stories are a way of getting children to learn for themselves. That is the case with the following:

- Reinforcing thinking strategies (comparing, classifying, predicting, planning etc.)

- Developing strategies for learning English (guessing the meaning of new words, training the memory etc.)

- Developing study skills (understanding and interpreting charts and graphs, organizing work and so on.).

Conclusion. Fairy tales are important literary icons in the English-speaking world. They were some of the first stories written in English and have continued to

enchant people of all ages. Thus, they are an invaluable resource for English classrooms when looked at from a cultural lens. Fairy tales offer valuable references which would be more difficult to encounter in stilted textbooks. They allow students to make comparisons of not only their culture with the target language, but between different target language cultures as well. Some tales may even be used to initiate self-reflection as students think about their roles and actions in society.

From the narrative structure to the context fairy tales bring out of the language, they are a sharp tool in the English teacher's toolkit. Grammar lessons could be conducted in a more engaging way as pupils fall into the fun and enchantment of fairy tales.

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